

SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH OF THE SCO COUNTRIES: SYNERGY AND INTEGRATION

上合组织国家的科学研究：协同和一体化

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企业活动中的现代信息技术：使用实践和威慑因素

**MODERN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE ACTIVITIES
OF ENTERPRISES: USAGE PRACTICES AND DETERRENENTS**

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摘要。21 世纪世界经济发展的主要特征之一是信息技术的快速发展以及工业生产和社会生活的几乎所有领域的密集数字化。这种情况无疑使开展研究以确定信息技术和数字经济产品在工业生产各个部门中使用的现代趋势变得有意义。

本研究的主要目标是证实在工业生产的各个部门扩大使用现代信息技术和数字经济产品的必要性，以及确定其在生产新型工业产品方面的有前景的应用领域。

研究的结果是，对工业企业活动中实施现代信息技术的主要方向进行了分析。确定了生产信息化和数字化方面的领先行业以及工业企业活动中使用的 IT 解决方案。确定了阻碍信息技术实施的主要因素并制定了克服这些因素的建议。

关键词：工业企业、行业、现代信息技术、使用实践、阻碍因素。

Abstract. *One of the key features of the development of the world economy in the 21-st century has been the rapid development of information technology and intensive digitalization of almost all areas of not only industrial production, but also the life of society. This circumstance undoubtedly makes it relevant to conduct research in terms of identifying modern trends in the use of information technologies and digital economy products in various sectors of industrial production.*

The main goal of this study is to substantiate the need to expand the use of modern information technologies and digital economy products in various sectors of industrial production, as well as to identify promising areas of their application for the production of new types of industrial products.

As a result of the study, an analysis of the main directions of implementation of modern information technologies in the activities of industrial enterprises was carried out. The leading industries in terms of informatization and digitalization of production and IT solutions used in the activities of industrial enterprises have

been identified. The main factors hindering the implementation of information technologies have been identified and proposals for overcoming them have been formulated.

Keywords: *industrial enterprises, industries, modern information technologies, practice of use, deterrent factors.*

Introduction

Modern information technologies (IT), digital economy products and integrated information and analytical management systems (II AMS) are becoming increasingly important tools in achieving strategic goals and solving problems of strategic development of industrial enterprises. They are used at all levels of management of industrial enterprises of a wide range of profiles and serve as an indispensable source of obtaining various types of information. The key feature of the functioning of modern IT, digital economy products and control information systems is the significant acceleration of the search for the required information, its processing and the adoption of management decisions on this basis. In addition, they have a fairly developed functional content. It is by expanding the range of functional characteristics of information support that modern IT and digital economy products allow industrial enterprises to increase the efficiency of their activities [1]. These features of modern IT and digital economy products contribute to the successful implementation of plans for the production of commercial products, the development of new types of products, the introduction of innovative technologies into production processes, entering new markets, improving interaction with counterparties, and reducing the costs of manufactured products.

Modern IT, digital economy products and control information systems used at industrial enterprises support the implementation of management decisions. At the same time, the continuous development and improvement of their functional characteristics imposes specific requirements and conditions on the production activities of industrial enterprises. The need to take them into account leads to changes in the operating parameters of the enterprises themselves.

Thus, the further development of modern IT, products of the digital economy and II AMS entails, on the one hand, the transformation of the production activities of enterprises up to the creation of new production facilities, and on the other hand, the expansion of the range of production activities of enterprises necessitates the timely processing of increasingly large volumes of various kind of information. The latter is no longer possible today without modern IT and digital economy products. In other words, the key factor in the successful operation of industrial enterprises is the symbiosis of product production and modern IT. Moreover, with a high degree of probability it can be argued that without the use of modern IT, products of the digital economy and automated control systems, the main branches

of industrial production will inevitably rapidly degrade. This conclusion is quite obvious, since in modern industrial enterprises most of the production processes are implemented through the use of modern IT and digital economy products.

Purpose of the study

The main goal of this study is to substantiate the need to expand the use of IT and digital economy products in various sectors of industrial production, to identify promising areas of their application for the production of new types of industrial products and the main factors limiting the process of their implementation.

Materials and methods

Currently, the management of most industrial enterprises in various industries is aware of the need to rethink the role of modern IT and digital economy products in organizing the entire complex of production processes. This is due to the expansion of the functionality of modern IT and digital economy products and their presentation as a key production resource. If in the early stages of use they performed mainly a service function, today modern IT and digital economy products directly influence the introduction of innovations and the choice of development strategies for industrial enterprises in the near future. The use of a wide range of IT solutions based on cloud technologies, artificial intelligence technologies, Big Data, blockchain, Internet of things and others opens up new opportunities for increasing the efficiency of production activity models of industrial enterprises. These models use a new computing and information processing infrastructure. It involves the digital transformation of all production processes, starting with the formation of production plans, their implementation, optimizing the consumption of all types of resources, increasing labor productivity and ending with financial accounting systems, automation of document flow and interaction with the enterprise's counterparties [2].

The need for accelerated implementation of modern IT and digital economy products in the activities of industrial enterprises in all sectors of the economy is also supported by the state. In July 2017, the government approved the "Digital Economy of the Russian Federation" program, which defines the main directions for the strategic development of the Russian economy until 2025 [3]. The main provisions of this document are aimed at developing digitalization processes both on the scale of the Russian economy as a whole, and at industrial enterprises in the context of its industries.

The materials analyzed in this study were quite widely presented in the open press publications on the main directions of development of modern IT and the use of digital economy products in the activities of industrial enterprises in a sectoral context. The work also used materials from current legislative and regulatory documents regulating the introduction of modern IT and digital economy products into the activities of industrial enterprises. In addition, the study used data from

one of the consulting structures to assess the limiting factors for the development of modern IT and the use of digital economy products.

The methodological basis for the research was the methods of an integrated approach, system analysis, processing and synthesis of information.

By modern IT we will understand a set of methods and software and technological tools that combine production and technological processes through the collection, storage, processing and presentation of information. The use of IT helps reduce the labor intensity of production processes through the use of information resources. The main goal of introducing modern IT into the production sector is to create favorable conditions for its development. It is implemented by intensifying the exchange of information, increasing the efficiency of its processing and use for making management decisions at the level of all structural divisions of industrial enterprises.

Results and discussion

Many experts admit that the speed of development of modern IT and digital economy products is rapidly increasing. In the coming years it will be possible to compare it with an exponential dependence. In a very short period of time, IT has revolutionized fundamental aspects of modern manufacturing. The irreversibility of information transformation and digitalization of production processes forces industrial enterprises in all sectors of the economy to adapt as quickly as possible to the new conditions of their activities. We specify the key areas of influence of modern IT on the development of industrial enterprises.

The emergence of mobile solutions has led to the use of digital economy products such as tablets and even smartphones to organize modern production. With the advent of mobile communications and broadband Internet, it has become possible to concentrate all production management functions on wearable devices: from organizing the production process itself to providing it with the necessary resources; from personnel management to improving their competencies; from conducting marketing campaigns to searching for new contractors; from selling products to improving methods of delivery; from maintaining financial records to assessing the efficiency of production activities. It turns out that mobile solutions can be used not only to manage the production activities of industrial enterprises, but also to generate demand for manufactured products from consumers.

With the advent of cloud computing, industrial enterprises have the opportunity to transfer the functions of processing large amounts of semi-structured information and variable data packages to third parties through cloud services on the Internet. This allows enterprises themselves to focus on optimizing production processes without worrying about the possible loss of important information. The availability of cloud computing resources opens up new opportunities for development for industrial enterprises. Meanwhile, just a few years ago, such opportunities were unacceptable for most enterprises due to their high cost.

Expanding the analytical capabilities of modern IT allows enterprises to analyze increasingly large volumes of information in a short time. The result of this is a deeper understanding of consumer needs and their structuring into more specific groups, which greatly facilitates the choice of development prospects for industrial enterprises. The emergence of increasingly sophisticated analytical services as part of digital economy products and II AMS allows enterprises to segment product markets with greater accuracy and gain additional competitive advantages.

Modern IT and digital economy products have made it possible to combine the information, hardware and software necessary for the formation of II AMS. Within the framework of these systems, new software solutions are appearing every day to optimize the production activities of industrial enterprises. As a rule, these solutions are easy to implement and their cost is quite affordable, which ultimately greatly facilitates the activities of industrial enterprises.

Industrial enterprises use modern IT and digital economy products to integrate intra-production communications. The functioning of II AMS makes it possible to combine into one network the interests of different structures of industrial enterprises, ranging from production departments and financial services, to personnel management and security services. With the growing number of online transactions, the importance of financial management and security services working together to improve the security of these types of transactions increases. Through the use of encryption and individual passwords, modern IT provides reliable protection of digital information for industrial enterprises. Access to information can only be obtained by persons vested with appropriate authority. With the development of modern IT, information security standards are also increasing [4]. The introduction of biometric security systems allows you to completely abandon the use of passwords. The choice of specific IT solutions to ensure reliable protection of digital information remains with the management structures of industrial enterprises.

A noticeable rise in digitalization in 2020 was associated with an active transition to remote work and online interaction, but IT itself was actively being implemented in enterprises even before the introduction of “Covid” restrictions. This is typical for enterprises in all industries. We can note the successful implementation of IT such as digital design and modeling, business process automation systems and the Internet of Things. Technologies actively implemented by many enterprises over the past five years include: additive technologies that speed up the production of material objects (for example, 3D printers); virtual and augmented reality technologies that help in marketing and presenting the experience of using the company’s product; unmanned systems; artificial intelligence (see Fig. [5]).

Figure. Use of digital technologies by implementation time (% of the number of organizations using the relevant technology)

Industry profile.

In terms of industry, the greatest successes in connection with the use of modern IT, digital economy products and II AMS have been achieved by enterprises in the military-industrial complex and the aviation industry. As a rule, enterprises in these industries are introducing new IT solutions for the first time, and also using elements of the digital economy paradigm. This allows enterprises in two industries to quickly change and reconfigure production processes, modernize their products, improve production technologies, and master the production of new types of products. Enterprises in these industries are not only provided with orders, but also receive financial support from the state for their successful implementation. The main goal of introducing new IT solutions and elements of the digital economy paradigm at enterprises of the military-industrial complex and the aviation industry is to reduce the cost of manufactured products, provided that the appropriate level of their quality characteristics is ensured. This is precisely what explains the priority implementation of MES and ERP class information systems into their production activities, which allow for more accurate accounting and control of all production costs, organizing operational planning and management of production capacity utilization, tracking the progress of sales of manufactured products in the context of individual types, for each order and for the enterprise as a whole.

Enterprises in the metallurgical, oil and gas and mining industries, when introducing new IT solutions and elements of the digital economy paradigm, are

focused on creating innovative value chains for their products. To solve this problem, they actively use Data Mining, Process Mining, BigData, Blockchain technologies, as well as virtual, augmented and mixed reality (VR - virtual reality, AR - augmented reality, MR - mixed reality). Thus, we can conclude that enterprises in these industries use a more in-depth approach to solve the problem of informatization and digitalization of their production activities.

Modern IT is also used in the mechanical engineering industry. Enterprises in this industry gain additional competitive advantages from using digital information as an important production resource. Information systems for design and technological preparation of production, machine learning, increasing production efficiency, industrial Internet of Things technologies, big data analysis platforms and a number of other information resources are being actively introduced into the production activities of enterprises in the mechanical engineering industry.

Today, an increasingly wider range of IT solutions is gradually being introduced into the production activities of industrial enterprises in almost all industries within the framework of the “Digital Enterprise” concept [3]. These solutions include information systems such as CRM, ERP, PLM, as well as production preparation and management systems. A distinctive feature of the functioning of these systems is the formation of a single information space. This circumstance ensures complete digital continuity of the entire production process, starting from the moment an order is received and ending with the release and sale of finished products. The use of this kind of information systems ensures comprehensive integration of production processes throughout the entire life cycle of manufactured products.

The competitive environment in the IT field dictates the need for constant development of companies in the context of innovation. “Leaders must understand market trends and changes, especially in an era of rapid development of science and technology, when the rate of substitution of goods and services is rapidly increasing” [6]. This is clearly illustrated by the example of Nokia, which for more than 100 years has been producing various goods: from paper to rubber and cables. This company began its calling in the 90s when it released its first mobile phone. Since then, Nokia has become the leader in the mobile phone segment. However, by the end of the last century, the company was unable to reorient production and responded too slowly to the advent of touch screens and new operating systems - iOS and Android. Attempts by management to keep up with competitors or to focus on cheap push-button models were unsuccessful. In 2014, the company was forced to sell its mobile phone division to Microsoft and announced it would no longer use the Nokia brand.

The introduction of modern IT into the activities of industrial enterprises in Russia is hampered by a number of factors. Among many others, we will highlight the most significant ones [7, 8].

Technological factor. There is always a risk that too fast a pace could overwhelm departments and result in all processes being brought to a standstill. If the pace is insufficient, there is a chance that you simply will not see the desired results and benefits (simplifying business processes and increasing income). As a result, enterprises lose interest in introducing innovations. When implementing IT, an enterprise can develop its activities more slowly than its direct competitors. To avoid this, you need to carefully analyze the market and competitors. This will help determine the desired pace and speed of IT implementation. Then you can gradually increase it, closely monitoring the overcoming of other barriers.

Human factor. This barrier takes into account the conservatism of the staff, which consists in the tendency of people to avoid sudden changes, changes in the usual foundations and work rules. There is also a lack of sufficient technological competencies among employees. The transition to IT also affects corporate culture. New technologies, processes and communications will change the entire organization and its structure.

When implementing IT, the human factor plays a big role, for example:

1) insufficient support from management;

Without the active participation of the company's leadership, digital transformation may not receive the necessary support and achieve its goals.

2) fear of change;

Managers may fear that new IT will disrupt existing business processes and company structure. It is important to assess the feasibility of IT implementation, identify the pros and cons, risks and benefits of the output.

3) lack of qualified personnel;

Often, enterprises are faced with a lack of qualified specialists capable of implementing modern IT, updating or building new technological processes. This requires either new specialists or training or retraining of existing employees. There is also a financial issue associated with this point, since it will be necessary to retrain personnel or resort to outsourcing services.

To overcome this barrier, staff should be prepared in advance and key employees trained who will be able to pass on the acquired experience and skills to other specialists. It is important not to forget to upgrade to modern equipment. The implementation of IT implies not only the transition to powerful hardware, but also the use of artificial intelligence technologies, blockchain, Internet of things, etc. This will help make the approach to IT implementation close to optimal.

Financial factor. The implementation of IT requires enterprises to make significant investments in material support, the development of new processes and development strategies, and employee training. Difficulties in financing these processes can be caused by various reasons, for example, low profit margins or a lack of understanding of the return on investment of a new IT implementation project. To address this issue, budget protection and risk management plans must

be carefully developed. Practice shows that the phased implementation of IT with the development of risk models for minimizing or circumventing risks will make financing not so difficult compared to the implementation of IT in one stage.

Information security factor. The introduction of IT not only opens up broad opportunities for the development of enterprises, but also creates many threats in terms of information security. The most common one is data leakage. This risk can also be attributed to both the human barrier - enterprises always require competent specialists, and the technological barrier - they need modern software that will protect against intruders. All this again comes back to finances. To overcome this barrier, a number of preventative and basic protective measures should be implemented. Preventive protection measures include: data backup, development and configuration of an access control system, both electronic and physical, preventing the relevance of the software used, encrypting information during its transmission and storage, etc. The main protection measures include: development and implementation of national secure systems, use of certified information security tools, updating and finalization of the company's regulatory framework. The implementation of these measures should be carried out in accordance with a pre-developed plan and taking into account the specific features of the enterprise's production activities.

Each enterprise is unique in its own way. Therefore, when implementing new IT, it is important to identify all priorities, develop a phased plan, ensure reliable financing, correctly allocate resources, take into account potential risks and threats, and ensure timely completion of the project.

Conclusion

The results obtained during the research allowed us to formulate the following conclusions.

1. In modern economic conditions, the use of modern IT in the production process becomes an important factor in the successful operation of industrial enterprises.

2. Expanding the functionality of modern IT and digital economy products turns information into the most important production resource, on which the introduction of innovations in industrial enterprises and the choice of strategies for their development directly depend.

3. A brief analysis of the main directions of the influence of modern IT on the development of industrial enterprises showed that it is realized through mobile solutions, cloud computing, expanding analytical capabilities, combining information, hardware and software, and integrating industrial communications.

4. In terms of industry, leading positions in informatization and digitalization of production are held by enterprises of the military-industrial complex, aviation, metallurgy, oil and gas, mining and engineering industries. In their production activities, enterprises in these industries use different IT solutions. At the same time,

an increasingly wider range of IT solutions is gradually being introduced into the production activities of industrial enterprises in almost all industries within the framework of the “Digital Enterprise” concept.

5. Four main factors (technological, human, financial and information security) have been identified that hinder the introduction of new IT into the activities of enterprises. However, in addition to them, there are quite a lot of other factors that enterprises must take into account when implementing IT, depending on the practical specifics of their production.

6. When implementing new IT, it is important to identify all priorities, develop a step-by-step plan, ensure reliable financing, correctly allocate resources, take into account potential risks and threats, and ensure timely completion of the project.

References

1. Ananyin V.I., Zimin K.V., Lugachev M.I., Gimranov R.D., Skripkin K.G. *Digital enterprise: transformation into a new reality // Business informatics*. 2018. No. 2(44). Pp. 45-54. DOI: 10.17323/1998-0663.2018.2.45.54.

2. Zhurakovskiy V. *Information technologies and their use in business management [Electronic resource]*. URL - <https://vc.ru/trade/72668-informacionnyetehnologii-i-ih-ispolzovanie-v-upravlenii-biznesom> (access date 18.07.2024).

3. Program “Digital Economy of the Russian Federation”. Approved by Decree of the Government of the Russian Federation dated July 28, 2017. No. 1632-r [Electronic resource]. URL: <http://static.government.ru/media/files/9gFM4FHj4PsB79I5v7yLVuPgu4bvR7M0.pdf>. (access date: 18.07.2024).

4. Kudinov A.A. *Problems of containing the development of innovations in the IT sphere // Issues of innovative economics*. 2020. Vol. 10. No. 3. Pp. 1803-1814. doi: 10.18334/vinec.10.3.110692.

5. *Digital technologies in business: practice and barriers to use. Monitoring digital business transformation. Issue 1. July 2023. // National Research University Higher School of Economics [Electronic resource]* URL: <https://issek.hse.ru/mirror/pubs/share/890550370.pdf?ysclid=lyr2it2j7y781160699> (access date 07.18.2024).

6. Makhlof Sukkar. *Analysis of the decline of Nokia from the point of view of marketing strategy // RMAT Bulletin*. 2019. No. 2. Pp. 52-58.

7. Mityaeva N.V., Zvodilo O.V. *Barriers to digital transformation and ways to overcome them // Bulletin of the Saratov State Socio-Economic University*. 2019. No. 3 (77). Pp. 22-24.

8. Filippov E.S. *Specification of barriers to digital transformation in an organization // Economics: yesterday, today, tomorrow*. 2022. Vol. 12. No. 3A. Pp. 486-493. DOI: 10.34670/AR.2022.39.11.056.